

#6

Evaluation & Impact Assessment
MOTIVATIONS REGISTER

<p>MAA Scenario</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Used iteratively throughout a project/initiative to assess and improve how actors/ stakeholders may be engaged.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Small to large multi actor group.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical skills required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Depends on group size & extent of discussion when drafting first version, if building a dedicated register. Then periodically updated throughout the project.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>The motivation register is maintained online, using a dedicated shared drive or online software such as Google Sheets.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 2, 3, 5.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: [Photo by Yan Krukov on Pexels.com](https://www.pexels.com/photo/young-man-writing-on-whiteboard/)

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Identify the motivations of actors/stakeholders – from their diverse perspectives – to become involved in an interactive innovation project.
- Build a register of these motivations, which is periodically updated, and to which all actors have access.
- Assist to design and plan project/initiative activities so that they are relevant to and motivate the whole range of different actors/stakeholders.
- Assess how project/initiative activities respond to motivations of different actor/stakeholder types.
- Inform adjustment of project/initiative activities so that they appropriately respond to the required diversity of actor/stakeholder types in a balanced way.
- Share the motivations register with other multi-actor initiatives so that knowledge about how to engage/incentivize actors/stakeholders to participate is shared.

Background and Logic

Traditional participants in research and innovation projects have been scientists and some other (typically government) actors whose habitual ‘day job’ involves participating in such projects. In the context of a wider ‘science governance’ movement, it is increasingly acknowledged that the pool of actors designing and implementing innovation projects must be diverse. Diversity ensures that the maximum variety of knowledges and perspectives are brought to bear on development problems and innovation opportunities. Through creatively combining knowledges, perspectives, ideas etc., the (interactive) innovation process is hugely enriched. Furthermore, for outputs of research, development or innovation projects to be taken up by end-users in society, representatives of such end-users must be directly involved or engaged with by projects.

To engage wide ranging actors and stakeholders in project/initiative activities, describing projects using academic or policy-making terms can have limited effectiveness. How can projects/initiatives (and individual activities/tasks) be described in ways that motivate actor/stakeholder types and incentivize them to engage? Even more importantly, how can projects/initiatives be designed in ways that truly do motivate actors/stakeholders? That the appropriate range of actors/stakeholders are enthusiastically involved is an important marker of how impactful in society a project/initiative will eventually be.

This tool – by building and periodically updating a register of the motivations of different actor/stakeholder types – aims to continuously attune project/initiative activities to the motivations of communities they serve. By responding to different motivations, actors/stakeholders engage better with and enrich projects/initiatives. Projects/initiatives are assessed on the basis of how well tools engage with the motivations of actors/stakeholders and are adjusted to ensure better and more representative/balanced engagement.

Materials

- Online register, pre-populated with names of actor/stakeholder types

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic & background of exercise.
- Optionally, show this [whiteboard animation on multi-actor work](#) or circulate the video in advance of the meeting where the Motivations Register will be discussed. This is to sensitise participants to the importance of interactive innovations to respond to different actor/stakeholder motivations

Step 2: Build/Modify a Motivations Register

- A bespoke/customised Motivations Register may be produced from scratch, or an existing Motivations Register (built by other interactive innovation projects) may be modified for the project.
- To build a register from scratch, follow the same steps taken in building the Needs Register (Tool #5)
- To modify an existing Motivations Register, show an existing register, such as the examples linked here:
 - » [AgriDemo:F2F \(Horizon 2020\) Motivations Register](#)
 - » [Plutos \(Horizon 2020\) Motivations Register](#)
- The Motivations Register may be built/adapted according to the nature and needs of the interactive innovation project in question, using appropriate actor/stakeholder categories (customised to the categories the project is tasked with engaging).
- Facilitate discussion among project partners to assess existing register, deleting or adding actor/stakeholder categories; and modifying motivations as needed.
- The output of this Step (2) is the first draft of the Motivations Register, which can be periodically updated and consulted for the design and assessment of project activities.
- Upload the (editable) version of the register on a shared drive, Google Sheets, or any other easily accessible online forum. Ensure that a field records who adds data to the register. This is to ensure that a balanced range of partners (from a multi-actor consortium) all add data to the register. Optionally, add a field to record *where/how* partners obtained the data in relation to motivations.

Step 3: Update the Motivations Register & Use it Internally

- Encourage partners (through regular reminders via correspondence and meetings) to visit the Motivations Register and to add to it. Partners elicit data on motivations through their interactions with actors/stakeholders (not from their own views on what they think motivates actors/stakeholders).
- Encourage partners to add their own motivations (in relation to project activities) to the register & discuss entries in discussions of project activities.

Step 4: Use the Motivations Register to Design and Assess Project/ Initiative Activities

- When project activities are being planned and designed, facilitate a discussion around the following topics:
 - » At this event/activity, will we be engaging with any actors/stakeholder or do we have an opportunity to engage? Which groups/types are they?
 - » Consulting relevant information in the Motivations Register, in what ways are the listed actor/stakeholder types likely to become interested in the event/activity?
 - » How can we modify the activity to incentivise better the motivated participation of each of the actor/stakeholder categories?
- In the aftermath of events/activities, facilitate a discussion around:
 - » How well did our event/activity respond to the motivations of actors/stakeholders?
 - » What worked particularly well, and what did not?
 - » In what ways/what was the evidence? (the evidence should be recorded/the Motivations Register amended accordingly)
 - » Did we gather any other evidence in relation to other motivations? (add them to the register accordingly)

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This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 773418. The responsibility for the information and views set out in this document lies entirely with the authors.